

**PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF EXPERT-PSYCHOLOGICAL CONVERSATION
WITH WITNESSES**

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Annotation: *The article reveals the psychological aspects of the process of interviewing witnesses during forensic psychological examination. Scientific literature and approaches to this problem have been analyzed.*

Keywords: *Witness, expertise, criminal situation, identity, testimony, criminal situation.*

Witness - Article 65 of the Code of Criminal Procedure stipulates that "any person who may be aware of a situation to be established in a criminal case may be summoned to testify" [1]. The typology of witnesses can be described as follows: "anonymous" witness; a witness who may be a participant in the crime; a witness who has a negative or positive attitude towards the accused (defendant); a witness who has a positive or negative attitude towards the activities of law enforcement agencies [2].

Various aspects of witnessing have been discussed in legal and psychological literature published abroad (R. Bull, R. Geiselman, I.A. Gorkovaya, G. Gross, G.G. Dospulov, V.F. Engalychev, O. Lipman, A. R. Luriya, R. Milne, G. Myunstenberg, A.R. Ratinov, V.V. Romanov, D. Reymond, O.D. Sitkovskaya, A.M. Stolyarenko, R. Fisher, E.N. Kholopova) and discussed in more detail in the literature of others. A number of factors affect the quantity and quality of information about the criminal situation that witnesses perceive and then describe: situational (criminal and postcriminal effects), personal, age-related, dysontogenetic. Their combined effect can lead to the appearance of dubious (due to a conscientious error of the witness in relation to the facts of the case) or false (perceived as untrue, but for some reason told as true) messages of the witness [3].

Criminal situation factor. Any situation of criminal significance has a number of features that make it difficult for participants to adequately perceive, remember, and then recover in speech:

1) objectively complex, multilevel and variable (dynamic) of the received information;

2) high level of involvement in events, or, conversely, the desire to stay away from what is happening;

3) non-standardity, unpredictability, extreme nature of the events for the participants, the events under investigation usually develop on the basis of conflict, associated with the appearance of aggression;

4) the individual emotional (emotional) and mental state (confusion, frustration, emotional tension, emotional agitation, etc.) of the participants during the perception of events.

Correct (adequate) perception of an event is influenced by the state of its occurrence, natural conditions: illumination, distance, field of view, the location of the observer, desensitizing factors [4]. The role of features such as witness age, life experience, interests, level of information and culture, psychophysical (mental and physical) characteristics of his sensory system, attention, memory, thinking, type and level of development of cognition, level of mastery of verbal methods of speech and information in general, the field of characterization (the presence of accents) and so on are very huge.

Understanding the criminal situation depends on the nature of the offender (who and in relation to whom, once or many times), the presence of specific psychiatric effects (acute mental injury or positive nature of events); depends on the subjective difficulty of understanding the significance of criminal events [5]. The level of understanding of the criminal component of an incident (event) affects the direction of cognitive processes during perception and recovery in memory: often people change the sequence of real events, generalize them, omit various details, some aspects they push forward, exaggerate some aspects of the object, replace the missing details with imaginary and arbitrary constructions [6].

Participating in a criminal situation is associated with the risk of death, seeing death, observation of brutal physical violence, humiliation and insults, and can lead to negative emotions (fear, shame, etc.), personal experiences, tension, frustration, confusion, emotional arousal (M. I. Enikeev, L.P. Konisheva, O.D. Sitkovskaya, L.B. Filonov, E.N. Kholopova, S.S. Shipshin). As a result, there may be evaluative elements in the description of the crime, exaggeration of the level of danger of the aggression committed, inconsistency in the description of the crime, a high level of emotionality and inconsistency in the description, a more "creative" reconstruction of events. For example, the phenomenon of "moving" or diffuse generalization ("everyone raped", "everyone hit") may occur. Often the sequence of events is sent by mixing (confusing), the symbols of one object are transferred to another. However, some details of the event can be perceived and remembered by the witness very clearly, sharply [7]. "At the same time, people often believe that their conclusions are true" [8].

The post-criminal situation factor. The components of the post-criminal situation include the socio-psychological environment that occurs around the work - the presence of external pressure or the influence of others, the lack of social assistance (support) [9]. In assessing the information obtained from a witness, it is extremely

important to analyze the events that took place in the period from the commission of the offense to the receipt of the first testimony, as well as the subsequent development of the situation.

The process of getting acquainted with the criminal situation, discussing it with relatives, getting information about the situation from the media, and even giving a testimony can change the attitude to the situation and the content of the story about the events. After all, over time, information from different sources in social memory becomes intertwined, and then it becomes difficult to separate the original data from the formed information.

Once the witness is in the spotlight, he or she can adjust his or her testimony to the information he or she expects to receive. This is often the case in children (they are more confident, i.e., on the one hand, prone to obey other people's demands without realizing it, on the other hand, are more susceptible to external influences, so they deliberately tell adults what they remember, not what they remember. [10]), as well as in people with underdeveloped mental capacity, lack of communication, accentuation in character. Witnesses may also be pressured (tried to persuade, threatened, bribed, etc.) by individuals interested in a particular development of the case.

The attitude of relatives and acquaintances to the criminal situation in many ways affects the nature of the story (testimony) of witnesses. "In some cases, group influence completely deprives a person of the ability to testify correctly." [11] Another important aspect is that in almost all categories of criminal cases, witnesses are persons who are familiar with the person under investigation (defendant), have some domestic or business relationship, which makes it difficult to take a position in assessing their actions, leading to a conflict of roles.

The situation is further complicated by the fact that the witness understands that his story about the events allows the decision on the case, that is, the conviction or acquittal of the person (defendant) under investigation [12]. This is especially important when the shows are given against relatives, against the wishes of other close people, because it negatively affects the relationship in the family - alienation occurs, the normal rhythm of life changes dramatically.

Age factor. "The younger the child, the greater the chance of misinterpreting events in a limited way" [13]. However, according to M.M. Kochenov, if the survey is organized in a quality and correct way, it is possible to get more detailed information from the child (even about events that he does not understand) [14].

The age of the person under examination determines the differences in the direction of his attention and memory, the organization of the sensory area. For example, children and adolescents better remember things and situations that stand out, and emotional aspects better than material expressed in words. When children remember events, they prioritize aspects of the thing that are not objectively important, but that they consider important.

In the preschool age, there are cases when the ability to perceive the perceived external side of events is delayed, or shifts in space and time, the meaning of which is not sufficiently understood by actual life experience and associations with the formed world image. The longer the time between the event and the animation, the greater the change in the animation. During this time, the child tries to understand events that he or she has experienced, but the content of which is unclear, as a result of which he or she makes his or her own hypotheses about the event and makes statements according to his or her own interpretations. This leads to a distortion of the animations. However, if the crime is committed more than once, but the factual side of such events is restored and time has elapsed, while displacements (shifts) and contamination are also observed, the events seem to “stick” to one event or a particular part of one episode and another part of another. are also given [15].

Children under the age of 5 often use vague concepts and comparisons, demonstrations in describing information. They are almost incapable of composing a coherent story independently, they do not understand the cause-and-effect relationships well, they describe events intermittently, they fill them with imaginary events that are formed on the basis of their understanding of what is happening. Some words are not used by children in a literal sense, but are used in accordance with the experience they have, which influences their family traditions. Even children under the age of 3 can describe what happened, even if it is not clear.

Younger school-age children are characterized by limited levels of comprehension of events during cognition and retelling. At this age, the child can tell not only the factual side of what happened, but also the content. Because it develops interrelated, logically coherent narrative skills. Preschoolers and young school-age children can be influenced (persuaded) by someone’s false testimony, but are often unable to tell the information they have absorbed when they repeat it without breaking it [16].

Children under the age of 12 are able to narrate and provide information as freely as adults, and are less likely to change their statements on guiding questions. Limited life experience and knowledge and imagination, insufficient development of adaptive ethical skills, perceptual capacity and long-term memory less than in adults in the description of information perception and recovery features, time intervals and sequences of events as less clear perceptions of spatial features of the object often leads to a tendency to make mistakes, to draw generalized conclusions on the non-existent signs of events. There is a strong focus on some aspects of the event, unusual events [17, 18].

Personality factor. This factor is often closely related to the age characteristics of the subject. Personal criteria that indicate that young (child) witnesses have limited ability to remember events (testify) and testify about them include strong confidence, obedience, a tendency to join the opinions of those around them, and sensitivity to

others' assessments of themselves [19]. The main components of the personal factor for adolescents are the insufficient formation of the motivational sphere; lack of formation of its own moral and ethical criteria and values; insufficient ability to predict their actions; is the presence of signs of strong confidence, submissiveness, conformity [20].

Dysontogenetic factor. In the semantic perception and understanding of the situation under investigation, various forms of mental anomalies (psychopathy, alcoholism, complications of skull and brain injury, mental retardation) leave a big mark on other aspects of the witness's mental activity. The more pronounced the deviations in mental and personal development, the greater the role they play in assessing the ability to testify and the actual possibility of its implementation at times of particular legal significance [21].

Thus, the analysis of our many years of expert practice shows that in the process of preparing for, conducting and analyzing the results of a psychologist-expert interview, the following important psychological conditions should be taken into account to minimize the breach of information about the situation of legal significance:

- external (social and physical) conditions of the survey;
- age, life and professional experience, level of education and culture of the person being examined;
- external (physical, socio-psychological) conditions of perception of the investigated phenomenon;
- the condition of the sensory apparatus, a description of the cognitive processes of the person being examined;
- the mental state of the person being examined during the perception and conversation;
- the relationship of the auditor with the participants of the legally significant situation;
- psychological and legal awareness of the expert on the nature of the incident;
- individual-psychological characteristics of the person being examined;
- reactions to the social environment that are important to the examinee.

The psychologist can obtain some information about these components during the analysis of working papers, and in the process of expert-psychological research, sufficient to evaluate the messages of the expert.

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